

THE SSSC SCIENCE COMPUTING HUB AND MATISSE: AN INTEGRATED PLATFORM FOR PLANETARY DATA ANALYSIS AND LANDING SITE SELECTION. G. Nodjoumi¹ V. Camplone¹, E. Rognini¹, M. Giardino², M. Perri¹, A. Zinzi² - ¹INAF/Osservatorio Astronomico di Roma (INAF-OAR), Via Frascati 33, 00078, Monte Porzio Catone (RM), Italy, ²Agenzia Spaziale Italiana (ASI), Via del Politecnico snc, 00133, Rome, Italy

Introduction: The continuous growth of high-resolution planetary datasets requires tools capable of integrating heterogeneous observations, spectral, morphological, thermal, and radar, within a coherent geodetic framework. Historically, planetary science workflows have been related to complex software stacks (e.g., ISIS, ASP) [1, 2] and heterogeneous data archives. To address these barriers, the Space Science Data Center (SSDC) of the Italian Space Agency (ASI) has deployed the Science Computing Hub (SciComHub) [3, 4]. This platform leverages the MATISSE (Multi-purpose Advanced Tool for the Instruments of the Solar System Exploration) [5, 6], framework to provide a web-based, reproducible environment for multi-mission data analysis and automated geoprocessing.

Infrastructure: The SciComHub serves as a centralized, web-based processing environment designed for scalability and reproducibility.

Containerization & Orchestration: Utilizing Docker and Podman, the hub ensures secure, isolated environments, with future plans to integrate SLURM for resource-intensive batch jobs and Kubernetes to handle concurrent usage.

Customized Environments: Users can switch between pre-configured images containing specialized tools: Planetary (USGS ISIS, NASA ASP, GDAL, and GRASS GIS) for DTM creation and mosaic projection, Astrophysical (specific libraries for galactic and stellar data reduction, including integration with SEDBuilder).

Legacy Support: Dedicated environments for Fortran, C, and C++ to preserve historical scientific algorithms.

GPU & Machine Learning: The infrastructure will be upgraded to support TensorFlow and PyTorch, enabling automated feature recognition (e.g., crater counting) via HPC hardware.

Analytical Engine: MATISSE is a GIS-oriented framework that enables 2D/3D data query, and visualization.

Geological Unit-Driven Analysis: A significant methodological shift in MATISSE is the ability to query data based on mapped geological units. By integrating global maps of Mercury, Ceres, and the Moon, Mars, users can retrieve datasets specifically falling within stratigraphic boundaries. This ensures that compositional and physical properties are interpreted within a rigorous geological context.

Crater-Based & Subsurface Exploration: Recent updates include crater-based searches, specifically

supporting the study of Mars's impact stratigraphy through catalogues of terraced craters.

Application Example - Landing Site Selection:

The integration of SciComHub and MATISSE will provide a standardised, FAIR-compliant (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) pipeline for landing site selection. Engineering Criteria: The pipeline automates the processing of Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) to derive slope limits, surface roughness, and illumination thresholds to ensure spacecraft safety. Scientific Priorities: Users can filter datasets by geological units to identify terrains that maximise analytical yield. The goal is to produce *Weighted Suitability Maps*, by combining these distinct layers into a unified GIS environment, the system generates suitability maps, enabling real-time collaboration between engineering and science teams. The landing site selection pipeline was initially developed and tested using lunar datasets, including high-resolution imagery and topography from the Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter (LRO/LROC), mineralogical data from Chandrayaan-1 M³, and global datasets such as Clementine and MOLA.

Future Directions: Future developments focus on:

Data Releases: The MATISSE catalogue is expanding to include 3D Digital Terrain Models (DTMs and VTP Meshes) from the ExoMars Trace Gas Orbiter's CaSSIS instrument, with a public release scheduled for Q1-Q2 2026. Additionally, a dedicated M³ continuum-removed dataset derived from Chandrayaan-1 will be released to support lunar surface studies.

Virtual Observatory (VO) Integration: Simplifying IVOA protocol adoption to allow researchers to publish products derived from SSDC datasets into the global Virtual Observatory.

AI/ML Integration: Leveraging artificial intelligence for predictive terrain modelling and automated feature recognition.

Federated Access: Implementing eduGAIN support for seamless institutional login for researchers worldwide.

Conclusion: By transitioning toward a reproducible, scalable pipeline, the SSDC SciComHub and MATISSE significantly reduce the risk of human error and the delays associated with heterogeneous data. This integrated approach establishes a collaborative

foundation for the next generation of Solar System exploration.

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References: [1] Sucharski T. et al. (2020) USGS-Astrogeology/ISIS3, ISIS 4.2.0 public release. [2] Beyer R. A. et al. (2018) *Earth and Space Science*, 5(9), 537–548. [3] Brandt C. H. et al. (2024) *Europlanet-Gmap/Docker-JupyterHub*, Zenodo. [4] Nodjoumi G. et al. (2025) *Earth and Space Science*, 12, e2025EA004251, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2025EA004251>. [5] A. Zinzi, M.T. Capria, E. Palomba, P. Giommi, L.A. Antonelli, (2016) *Astronomy and Computing*, Volume 15, 2016, Pages 16-28, ISSN 2213-1337. [6] V. Campione, A. Zinzi, M. Massironi, A.P. Rossi, F. Zucca, (2024) *Astronomy and Computing*, Volume 48, 2024, 100852, ISSN 2213-1337.